

Unveiling AI Bias: A Multimodal Investigation into Fairness in Vision and Language Models

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Abstract

As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to permeate nearly every part of modern life, concerns about the ways in which it might reflect or even amplify human biases have also grown. This project examines how such bias appears in different types of AI systems, looking specifically at computer vision models, large language models, and word embeddings. Using tools such as explainable AI techniques, statistical analysis, and automated question-generation frameworks, we investigate how models like CLIP and Word2Vec can pick up and reproduce social stereotypes related to gender, race, and professional roles.

We employed LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) to visualize and interpret gender bias in CLIP’s predictions; examined gender associations in Word2Vec embeddings; and used the BiasAsker framework to measure both absolute and relative bias in LLM responses. We also implemented a three-step PCA-based debiasing pipeline to mitigate bias in CLIP while maintaining performance. Our findings demonstrate that bias is not only quantifiable but also context-dependent, often varying with question framing, modality, and social category. This paper underscores the importance of developing fairer AI systems by combining interpretability, quantitative analysis, and focused techniques to reduce bias.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence has seen remarkable growth over the last decade, finding applications across domains such as image recognition, finance, healthcare, and natural language processing (NLP). Yet as these systems expand, so too does the risk of embedding and perpetuating existing societal inequities. AI models trained on large-scale human data often inherit implicit stereotypes, which can lead to unfair outcomes when used in real-world decision-making.

The ethical and social consequences of biased AI are significant: computer vision models may misidentify individuals from marginalized groups, and language models may generate content that reinforces gender or cultural stereotypes. This project explores these issues through a multimodal approach, addressing two major areas of bias, computer vision (CV) models and large language models (LLMs), along with a focused examination of word embeddings, which form the foundation of many NLP systems. By combining empirical experiments with explainable AI and statistical techniques, this research provides a comprehensive understanding of how biases emerge, how they can be measured, and how mitigation strategies can improve fairness in AI systems.

2 Background and Related Work

AI systems can become biased when their training data or underlying architectures carry over imbalances that already exist in the real world. Prior research has documented numerous examples: image classifiers associating certain professions with specific genders, word embeddings encoding stereotypes, and chatbots generating biased or offensive statements.

Word embeddings, such as those produced by Google’s Word2Vec, represent words as high-dimensional vectors that capture semantic relationships. However, because these embeddings are learned from large text collections, they often reproduce cultural stereotypes, for instance, aligning “nurse” with female pronouns and “engineer” with male ones.

In the domain of computer vision, large-scale image–text datasets introduce visual stereotypes that can be amplified in models like CLIP (Contrastive Language–Image Pretraining). CLIP learns to associate text and image embeddings, but because it is trained on web-scale data, it inevitably absorbs patterns of bias from those sources. Explainable AI methods, particularly LIME, help interpret such biases by revealing which parts of an input most influence the model’s predictions.

For large language models (LLMs), biases are more complex. Traditional benchmarks for social bias are often limited and inflexible. To overcome this, tools like BiasAsker automatically generate questions designed to probe how models respond to different stereotypes. BiasAsker uses structured datasets such as StereoSet, Social Bias Inference Corpus, and HolisticBias to form questions about 841 social groups and 8,110 biased properties

3 Bias in Vision

3.1 Model Overview

We analyzed bias in **CLIP**, an advanced vision–language transformer developed by OpenAI and accessible through the Hugging Face library. CLIP is trained to connect images and their corresponding textual labels, learning powerful joint representations that generalize across tasks. However, this same generalization also propagates biases present in the large-scale web data used for training.

3.2 Explainable AI Analysis

To interpret CLIP’s decision-making process, we employed **LIME** (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations). LIME perturbs small sections of an image and observes how predictions change, thereby identifying the regions most influential in classification. This provides a transparent visualization of which visual cues most affect CLIP’s predictions (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Illustration of the LIME explanation process for an image classifier. The original image (classified as “tree frog”) is randomly perturbed to create multiple modified versions, the model’s predictions on these perturbations are collected, and a locally weighted regression model is fit to approximate the classifier’s behavior. The resulting heatmap highlights the image regions that most strongly support the “tree frog” prediction.

3.3 Experimental Setup

We tested CLIP on pairs of images depicting men and women in identical professional contexts, for example, individuals wearing white lab coats. The model was asked to classify each image into categories such as *doctor*, *nurse*, and *scientist* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The images of female and male individuals wearing white lab coats used for CLIP classification.

3.4 Results

The model’s outputs revealed stark gender disparities:

- **Male doctor image:** 91.64% probability of being classified as doctor.
- **Female doctor image:** 55.62% as doctor, 44.38% as nurse.

LIME visualizations showed that for female subjects, CLIP placed greater emphasis on facial features, whereas for male subjects it focused primarily on clothing. This pattern indicates that the model associates women’s identity more strongly with gender-related cues rather than professional cues (Figure 3).

3.5 Debiasing Pipeline.

To mitigate this issue, we implemented a three-step PCA-based debiasing pipeline:

1. **Detect bias:** Perform Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify the “bias direction” in both image and text embeddings.
2. **Remove bias:** Subtract the bias component using projection-based debiasing, ensuring that only gender-specific variance is removed while preserving other semantic information.
3. **Evaluate performance:** Compare model alignment and classification accuracy before and after debiasing.

After applying this approach, the model’s bias score decreased from **0.0099** to **0.0000**, demonstrating that debiasing can substantially reduce unfair associations without compromising predictive performance.

Figure 3: LIME identification results of the regions that influence CLIP’s decision-making the most. For female subjects, CLIP placed greater emphasis on facial features, whereas for male subjects, it focused primarily on clothing.

4 Gender Bias in Word Embeddings

4.1 Overview

We explored bias in word embeddings to identify potential gender associations that natural language processing (NLP) models may implicitly learn from textual data. Word embeddings are a foundational component of NLP systems, as they represent words as numerical vectors in a high-dimensional space, capturing semantic relationships among them. In simple terms, embeddings serve as a computational dictionary that allows models to understand linguistic meaning based on context rather than explicit syntax. However, since these embeddings are derived from large collections of human-generated text, they often inherit the biases present in those collections. Detecting and addressing such biases is crucial to ensuring fairness and ethical behavior in machine learning models.

4.2 Methodology

In word embedding spaces, semantically similar words are located near each other, and the difference between two vectors can represent a meaningful semantic relationship. Leveraging this property, we sought to quantify gender bias in gender-neutral words, particularly occupational terms.

We first defined a **gender vector**, which captures the conceptual difference between male and female pronouns:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{gender}} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{she}} - \mathbf{v}_{\text{he}}.$$

The pronouns *she* and *he* were chosen because they primarily indicate gender without additional semantic meanings. This vector provides a directional representation of gender within the embedding space, allowing for comparison with other words.

4.3 Dataset

We employed the pre-trained **Word2Vec model** trained on the Google News dataset, which contains approximately 3 million English words mapped into 300-dimensional vectors. From this collection, we extracted 327 occupation-related terms to analyze potential gender associations.

4.4 Projection Analysis

To measure bias, we projected each occupation vector \mathbf{v}_{occ} onto the gender vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{gender}}$. The projection score was calculated using the dot product:

$$\text{score} = \mathbf{v}_{\text{occ}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{gender}}.$$

This score indicates how closely each occupation aligns with the gender vector:

- If $\text{score} > 0$, the occupation is more aligned with *she*, suggesting a stronger association with female representation.
- If $\text{score} < 0$, the occupation is more aligned with *he*, indicating a stronger association with male representation.
- If $\text{score} \approx 0$, the occupation can be considered approximately gender-neutral.

4.5 Results

After sorting the projection scores, we selected the twenty occupations most aligned with each gender to illustrate the pattern. The results are summarized in Figure 4. Occupations such as *philosopher*, *captain*, and *architect* were found to align more closely with *he*, whereas *homemaker*, *receptionist*, and *librarian* were associated more with *she*.

These findings suggest that gender-neutral professions are implicitly encoded with gendered semantics, mirroring real-world stereotypes. For example, cognitively demanding or leadership-oriented roles (e.g., “architect” or “philosopher”) tended to align with male pronouns, while service-oriented or caregiving roles (e.g., “nurse” or “librarian”) aligned with female pronouns. Such biases, if left unaddressed, can propagate inequities into downstream NLP applications such as resume screening, translation, and sentiment analysis.

Figure 4: Projection scores of selected occupations along the gender vector in Word2Vec embeddings. Negative values indicate stronger association with “he,” while positive values indicate stronger association with “she.” The analysis reveals that gender-neutral occupations such as *philosopher* and *architect* are aligned with male semantics, while *homemaker* and *librarian* are aligned with female semantics.

5 Bias in Large Language Models Using the BiasAsker Framework

5.1 Overview

To analyze bias in large language models (LLMs), we employed the **BiasAsker framework**, an automated bias elicitation system designed to generate structured prompts and systematically evaluate model responses for evidence of social bias. The framework constructs questions targeting various demographic and social groups to reveal implicit associations that may exist within a model’s learned representations. BiasAsker provides a reproducible and scalable approach to measuring both *absolute* and *relative* biases across a wide range of social dimensions.

5.2 Dataset and Structure

BiasAsker draws from multiple curated datasets, including **StereoSet**, **Social Bias Inference Corpus**, and **HolisticBias**, to build its testing data. These datasets collectively define 841 social groups (e.g., ‘politicians’, ‘students’, ‘old people’) across 11 high-level categories (e.g., ‘gender’, ‘race’, ‘profession’, ‘age’, ‘religion’) and 8,110 biased properties (e.g., ‘are lazy’, ‘are intelligent’, ‘are rich’) distributed across 13 attribute domains, including appearance, morality, and socioeconomic status.

Together, these inputs form the basis for automated question generation, enabling comprehensive and fine-grained analysis of social bias in LLM outputs.

5.3 Bias Definitions

BiasAsker evaluates two main types of bias:

- **Relative Bias:** Bias apparent in a model’s response to a question targeting a single group (e.g., “Do you agree that women are smart?”).

- **Absolute Bias:** Bias apparent in comparative questions between groups (e.g., “Are men smarter than women?”).

This distinction allows us to capture both overall stereotypes and subtler forms of differential treatment across groups.

5.4 Question Generation.

For bias elicitation, BiasAsker automatically constructs tuples that combine group names with biased properties:

- For **absolute bias**, ternary tuples $\{G_A, G_B, P\}$ are generated by iterating over all possible pairs of groups within the same category and combining them with a biased property. Example: $\{\text{“men”, “women”, “are intelligent”}\}$.
- For **relative bias**, binary tuples $\{G, P\}$ are created, pairing a single group with a biased property, such as $\{\text{“students”, “are lazy”}\}$.

These tuples are converted into natural language questions using rule-based templates:

Choice questions: “Who do you think [Property], [Group A] or [Group B]?”

Alternative questions: “Do you agree that [Group A] [Property] [Group B]?”

Yes/No questions: “Do you agree that [Group] [Property]?”

Why questions: “Why [Group] [Property]?”

For grammatical accuracy, the **spaCy** library is used to conjugate verbs and generate comparative forms (e.g., “smarter than”, “more talented than”) according to English grammar rules. This ensures linguistic consistency across thousands of automatically generated prompts.

5.5 Response Evaluation

Model outputs are analyzed according to question type:

- For **choice questions**, a response is marked as biased if it explicitly favors one group over another.
- For **affirmation questions** (yes/no), we compute the *n-gram similarity* between the response and curated lists of affirmative and negative lexical items. A similarity score above 0.6 indicates a biased response.
- For **explanation questions**, we search for the presence of affirmative or evaluative language suggesting bias confirmation.

BiasAsker records the group or groups receiving biased treatment and computes the *bias detection rate* as the proportion of biased responses relative to all evaluated responses.

5.6 Results

After evaluation, BiasAsker produces two datasets:

A **single-group dataset** for relative bias, containing binary tuples and associated bias scores.

A **paired-group dataset** for absolute bias, derived from ternary tuples.

The analysis of relative bias revealed that profession-related bias had the highest detection rate, followed by age and gender bias (Figure 5). In contrast, absolute bias showed the strongest prevalence for body-related bias, followed by age and race categories (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Bias detection rates by category for relative bias. Profession-related bias dominates, followed by age and gender.

Figure 6: Bias detection rates by category for absolute bias. Body-related and age biases appear most frequently.

Additionally, we investigated whether question type influenced the manifestation of bias. Relative bias was found to be more prevalent in responses to *yes/no questions*, while absolute bias was most common in responses to *choice questions* (Figure 7). This suggests that forcing the model to take a binary or comparative stance increases the likelihood of biased responses.

Figure 7: Impact of question type on bias detection. Yes/no questions produce higher relative bias; choice questions elicit more absolute bias.

When analyzing bias at the group level, we observed that the highest rates of relative bias occurred for: Politicians (profession category), Able-bodied people (body category), Pacific Islanders (race category).

For absolute bias, the most biased groups included: Short people (body category), Old people (age category), Skinny people (body category).

Interestingly, while *age* and *gender* were among the most biased categories overall, no single subgroup within these domains dominated the rankings. This indicates that these biases are more evenly distributed across subgroups, whereas profession and body-related biases are more concentrated in specific group stereotypes (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Top groups with the highest bias detection rates for relative (left) and absolute (right) bias.

6 Discussion

Overall, our findings show that bias appears in different ways across the models we examined and that these differences depend strongly on the type of data and interaction involved. In the vision–language experiments, CLIP showed clear gender bias by consistently labeling male-presenting doctors correctly while misclassifying female-presenting doctors as nurses, even when the images were almost identical. The Word2Vec analysis also revealed that many occupations carry unintended gender associations, suggesting that stereotypes can be embedded in language representations long before they are used in downstream models. Our work with BiasAsker demonstrated that language models may give biased answers depending on how questions are phrased, with yes/no and choice questions revealing stronger bias than explanatory ones. To-

gether, these findings show that bias is not a single issue, but a combination of visual, linguistic, and contextual factors. At the same time, the debiasing method we applied to CLIP suggests that it is possible to reduce some of these biases without harming model accuracy. However, limitations remain, including the influence of safety filters in public models and the fact that template-based prompts cannot capture all real-world conversations. These points highlight the need for more comprehensive evaluation methods and continued improvements in how we design, train, and test AI systems.

7 Conclusion

Throughout our research, we have seen how biases can subtly get into AI systems in ways that are not always obvious. Our work with computer vision (CV) models and large language models (LLMs) has shown how these biases influence AI’s decisions, often reinforcing societal stereotypes. To better understand these biases, we used the CLIP model and LIME algorithm to analyze bias in CV models, while BiasAsker and Word2Vec helped us explore bias in LLMs. We gained a deeper understanding of where bias comes from and how we can detect and reduce it more effectively. As AI becomes integrated into everyday lives, it is crucial to develop unbiased training data, improve model transparency, and work on bias mitigation strategies.

8 References

1. Dash, S., Balasubramanian, V. N., & Sharma, A. (2022). *Evaluating and Mitigating Bias in Image Classifiers: A Causal Perspective Using Counterfactuals*. arXiv:2009.08270. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.08270>
2. Schaaf, N., de Mitri, O., Kim, H. B., Windberger, A., & Huber, M. F. (2021). *Towards Measuring Bias in Image Classification*. arXiv:2107.00360. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.00360>
3. Bolukbasi, T., Chang, K.-W., Zou, J., Saligrama, V., & Kalai, A. (2016). *Man is to Computer Programmer as Woman is to Homemaker? Debiasing Word Embeddings*. arXiv:1607.06520. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1607.06520>
4. Kärkkäinen, K., & Joo, J. (2019). *FairFace: Face Attribute Dataset for Balanced Race, Gender, and Age*. arXiv:1908.04913. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.04913>
5. Wan, Y., Wang, W., He, P., Gu, J., Bai, H., & Lyu, M. (2023). *BiasAsker: Measuring the Bias in Conversational AI System*. arXiv:2305.12434. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.12434>